

INFLUENCE OF THE FUNCTIONAL PROBIOTIC FEED ADDITIVE “PROBIOCELL” ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT, PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS AND MEAT PRODUCTIVITY OF RABBITS

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Abstract. For the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the possibility of using the domestic probiotic feed additive “PROBIOCELL” in the diet of rabbits was studied. A positive effect of the supplement on hematological parameters and the state of natural resistance of the rabbits’ organism has been established. The use of the probiotic feed additive “PROBIOCELL” will allow participation in the state import substitution program. This domestic feed additive will contribute to the increase in animal productivity and high efficiency of therapeutic measures.

Keywords: probiotics, cellulolytic bacteria, feed additive, veterinary science, digestion, zootechnical indicators, hematology, immunology.

Relevance of the topic. At the present stage in Uzbekistan, the most pressing issue is providing the population with high-quality livestock products.

One of the promising branches of agriculture in Uzbekistan is rabbit breeding, the main product of which is high-quality dietary meat, as well as raw materials for fur products: skins and down. Rabbits are highly fertile and early-maturing, which makes it possible to obtain a significant amount of slaughter products in a short time. Over 70 kg of meat, over 30 heads of rabbits, and therefore over 30 skins can be obtained from one female rabbit per year.

Currently, in the field of rabbit breeding, the breeding and keeping of rabbits has been studied best, while the issues of their feeding and, to a relatively lesser extent, the influence of various feed additives on the animal’s body have been studied less. The intensive development of the rabbit breeding industry began thanks to modern effective developments in feeding, technology of keeping and raising animals with the aim of improving and increasing the productivity of animals.

The modern feed market offers various components to increase the nutritional value of the diet and its effectiveness. Such components include protein-rich yeast, functional probiotic feed additives [1-6]. Their energy value is close to grain feed, and in terms of protein content they are not inferior to soybean meal and other traditional feed additives. Feed and hydrolytic yeast and probiotics are a source of not only protein, but also essential amino acids and B vitamins.

Cellulose is not digested by itself in the body of herbivorous plants, so cellulose-destroying bacteria live in their stomachs. Under the action of enzymes of these bacteria, cellulose is destroyed. This type of relationship is called symbiosis. Since both organisms benefit from each other. Cellulolytic bacteria isolated from animals are of great interest and have prospects for wide use in domestic feed production. In the laboratory of microbiology and biotechnology of probiotics of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a

number of studies were conducted on the isolation and study of cellulolytic bacteria from domestic animals [14-17].

There is little information about the use of yeast biomass in feeding rabbits. The relevance of the research lies in studying the influence of different amounts of yeast biomass on the productivity indicators and meat qualities of rabbits under intensive rearing technology [18].

Recently, the use of probiotic feed additives, which have the ability to optimize the body's metabolic processes, improve digestion, as well as treat and prevent gastrointestinal diseases and restore normal intestinal microflora, has become increasingly relevant to solve this problem.

One of the relatively new domestic probiotic feed additives, developed by the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is "PROBIOCELL", consisting of cellulolytic bacteria isolated from domestic animals and probiotic cultures. This composition of the drug is new and, due to the lack of sufficient study, has not yet found wide use in rabbit breeding and other sectors of domestic animal husbandry. In this regard, the study of the influence of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" on the biological and productive qualities of rabbits is relevant and timely.

Level of development of the topic. We have conducted research on the use of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL", which contains a microbial mass of live spore-forming cellulolytic bacteria of the genus *Bacillus subtilis* and local probiotic strains of *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Pediococcus acidilactici*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* and bacteria of the genus *Weissella*. Given the problem of providing the population with high-quality livestock products, the use of probiotics is of scientific and practical interest. The use of various probiotics on the body of farm animals has been studied quite widely, but the use of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" in industrial rabbit breeding remains unstudied.

The purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of this work was a comparative assessment of the biological and productive qualities of rabbits using different doses of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL". The following tasks were solved:

- to study the characteristics of growth, development and safety of rabbits when introducing different doses of the probiotic "PROBIOCELL" into their diet;
- to determine the interior indicators of young rabbits;
- to determine meat productivity.

Scientific novelty of the work. As a result of complex studies, optimal doses and positive influence of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" on the safety of the rabbit population, digestibility of nutrients in the diet, meat productivity and meat quality were established.

Research methods. The methodology of the conducted research is based on scientific principles set out in the works of researchers on the topic under study.

In the course of our research, we used well-known and special methods. The digital material was processed based on statistical and mathematical methods of analysis using the Microsoft Office software package and determining the Student reliability criterion at three probability levels.

Research results.

The study was conducted at the Selection and Genetic Center for Rabbit Breeding at the Institute of Animal Husbandry and Poultry Farming of the Republic of Uzbekistan on local rabbit breeds. Three groups of 45-day-old rabbits were formed: Group I was a control group, raised without the use of a probiotic; Group II was raised with the addition of a 1% probiotic feed additive

to the main diet, and Group III was raised with the addition of 2% probiotic feed additive to the main diet.

Of greatest interest for research is the dynamics of changes in live weight, which characterizes the degree of development of a living organism during the period of ontogenesis. Monitoring of live weight dynamics was carried out by individual weighing every 15 days.

The studies showed that adding the probiotic "PROBIOCELL" to the diet of the experimental groups of rabbits had a growth-stimulating effect. Thus, already 15 days after the start of feeding the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL", the rabbits of the first group were inferior in live weight to their peers of the second group - by 18 g (0.88%), the third group - by 21 g (1.02%).

Later, the intergroup differences increased. Thus, at the age of 105 days, the rabbits of group III had the greatest live weight. They exceeded the rabbits of control group I by 69 g (2.36%, $P < 0.05$), and group II by 19 g (0.63%).

In subsequent age periods, the intergroup trend of increasing live weight of rabbits was preserved, and the differences became more pronounced. At the age of 150 days, the advantage in the studied trait was on the side of the experimental groups, and the animals of group III had the highest indicators. At the age of 150 days, they exceeded their peers in the control group in live weight by 138 g (3.82%, $P < 0.001$), and those in group II by 45 g (1.21%).

From the data obtained, it can be concluded that the introduction of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" into the diet of rabbits has a positive effect on the level of live weight.

The lowest absolute increase in live weight was observed in rabbits of group I (control), and this trend was observed throughout the entire study. In the first 15 days of the experiment, the rabbits in the control group were inferior in this indicator to their peers in group II by 10 g (2.30%), and in group III by 25 g (5.77%; $P < 0.001$).

Studying the blood picture dynamically and in combination with other data, in connection with the factors influencing these characteristics, provides information that can be used to manage processes that affect the productivity of the animal. Based on this, we studied the morphological and biochemical parameters of the blood of experimental rabbits.

The data we obtained and their analysis indicate a change in the morphological composition of the blood when the probiotic "PROBIOCELL" is included in the diet. It is worth noting that at the beginning of the experiment, the parameters studied in rabbits of all experimental groups differed insignificantly and were within the physiological norm. The results of the studies show that the inclusion of the probiotic "PROBIOCELL" in the diet of rabbits has a certain effect on hematological indices, which is primarily due to the unequal growth intensity. The level of erythrocytes and hemoglobin in the blood is closely related to the productivity of animals.

We found that at the end of the experiment, the rabbits in the experimental groups had higher concentrations of erythrocytes and leukocytes, as well as a higher level of hemoglobin, which corresponds to a higher level of metabolism in the body, an increase in live weight and increased resistance. Thus, rabbits of the second experimental group had an advantage over their peers of the control group in terms of the level of erythrocyte content by $0.54 \cdot 10^{12}/l$ (10.54%; $P < 0.05$), and those of the third group – by $1.00 \cdot 10^{12}/l$ (19.53%; $P < 0.001$). The level of leukocytes in the blood of experimental animals at the end of the experiment was $6.94 \cdot 10^9/l$ for animals of the first control group, $7.34 \cdot 10^9/l$ for group II, and $7.50 \cdot 10^9/l$ for group III, which is higher than the

control group analogues by 0.40 109/l (5.76%; P 0.05) and 0.56 109/l (8.06%; P 0.01) for groups II and III, respectively.

At the current stage of animal husbandry development, the use of various probiotic supplements is becoming relevant [7-13]. The widespread use of probiotics in animal husbandry and veterinary medicine is due to their safety and harmlessness to the body.

In our studies, rabbits from all experimental groups were provided with optimal feeding and maintenance conditions that promoted normal growth and development of the animals. Over the 90-day experimental period, the advantage of the rabbits of the second experimental group over their peers of the first control group in terms of consumption of feed units was 1.59%, exchange energy - 3.12 MJ (1.61%), dry matter - 0.25 kg (1.61%), crude protein - 0.05 kg (1.63%), the advantage of the rabbits of the third group was 0.74 units (3.57%); 7.00 MJ (3.61%); 0.56 kg (3.61%); 0.11 kg (3.59%), respectively.

The inclusion of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" in the diet has increased the productivity of rabbits and also increased their growth. As a result of the conducted research, it was established that the rabbits of the experimental groups that received the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" had a greater live weight, compared to their peers in the control group at the age of 75 days by 18-22 g (0.88-1.07%), 90 days - by 35-49 g (1.41-1.97%), 105 days - by 50-69 g (1.71-2.36%), 120 days - by 64-96 g (1.97-2.95%), 135 days - by 75-113 g (2.17-3.26%) and 150 days - by 93-138 g (2.57-3.82%). The established differences in the live weight indicators of the experimental and control group rabbits were the result of the favorable effect of the probiotic "PROBIOCELL". When studying the dynamics of the average daily gain in live weight of rabbits, it was established that up to the age of 105 days, its stable increase was observed. Subsequently, this indicator decreases, which is due to their physiological state and the intensification of fat deposition processes in the body. Moreover, in terms of average daily gain, the rabbits in the experimental groups exceeded their peers in the control group at the age of 105 days by 1.0-1.3 g (3.37-4.39%), and at the age of 150 days by 0.6-1.1 g (5.5-10.09%).

Studies of exterior features have shown that at the beginning of the experiment, no significant differences in the main measurements were observed, but at the age of 150 days, the rabbits in the experimental groups exceeded their peers in the control group in body length by 0.5-1.3 cm (0.80-2.10%), in chest girth by 1.1-1.8 cm (3.00-4.91%), and in the index of compactness by 1.31-1.66%.

Different growth rates of the skeleton and muscles affected the nature of changes in body condition indices. The advantage of group II rabbits over their peers in group I at the age of 150 days was 1.31% (P 0.01), and group III rabbits were 1.66% (P 0.001). In our opinion, all exterior changes occurred as a result of the influence of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL", which increased their meat productivity. The obtained data are consistent with the general biological patterns of rabbit development and the results of other researchers who studied the comparative aspect of the exterior of rabbits under optimal growing conditions.

The inclusion of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" in the diet of rabbits increased their viability compared to the control group analogues. Significant loss was observed at the beginning of the experiment, but in the experimental groups this indicator was significantly lower, and the survival rate was 100%. The study of the ethological reactivity of young rabbits shows that, despite the same conditions of maintenance and feeding, the rhythm of vital manifestations in animals of different groups is not the same. Thus, the rabbits of the control group

spent more time on consuming feed than the rabbits of the experimental groups by 12-15 minutes (4.31-5.64%). It should be noted that the rabbits of the experimental groups rested more by 11-22 minutes (1.32-2.65%).

The data obtained in the study of the ethological reactivity of rabbits when introducing different doses of the probiotic feed additive "PROBIOCELL" into their feed indicate that there is a certain intergroup difference in the duration of individual elements of behavior, which is due to the action of this additive and the manifestation of a genetic instinct to create more comfortable conditions.

Blood as one of the types of tissues of the internal environment is of great importance for the life of the animal organism, due to which the metabolism is carried out. Research has established that the morphological and protein composition of the blood of rabbits of all experimental groups was within the physiological norm. It is also worth noting that at the beginning of the experiment, the blood of rabbits in all groups contained fewer erythrocytes and leukocytes, and the level of hemoglobin, total protein and albumin was lower.

At the end of the experiment, the rabbits of the experimental groups had higher concentrations of erythrocytes by 0.34-1.00 10¹²/l (10.34-19.53%), leukocytes by 0.370-0.46 10⁹/l (5.66-8.06%), as well as higher levels of hemoglobin by 7.42-11.08 g/l (6.81-10.08%) and total protein by 2.40-4.48 (3.64-6.42%), which corresponds to a higher level of metabolism in the body, an increase in live weight and increased resistance.

Conclusions. The use of the probiotic complex "PROBIOCELL" in an optimally selected dosage of 2.0 g / kg in the composition of compound feed had a positive effect on the growth rate, physiological status of the body and quality indicators of rabbit meat, which may be the basis for its further use in industrial conditions.

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